

ESR of Ion Cluster Equilibria in Semiquinone Alkali Metal Systems

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Well resolved ESR spectra have been observed from samples of semiquinones produced by alkali metal reduction of quinones in ether solvents like dimethoxyethane and tetrahydrofuran *in vacuo*. The presence of solvated ion pairs and contact ion pairs has been established. The equilibria existing among the different species and the line width effects observed in the ESR spectra of the different species are discussed.

Ion-pairing in semiquinone alkali metal systems has attracted the attention of several investigators¹⁻⁷. In most of these investigations attention was focussed mainly on the structures of ion pairs and on the reactions of the ion pairs within the system, i.e., reactions between different types of ion pairs from the same parent molecule or reactions between ion pairs and their parent molecule. In addition, a wealth of information can be obtained as regards spin density redistribution arising from ion pair association⁸ and in the present paper we shall describe some recent studies on durosemiquinone (DSQ)⁻ and parabenzosemiquinone (PBSQ)⁻ radicals produced by potassium metal reduction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Duroquinone was produced from durene by the well known methods. DME and THF were used as solvents. The duroquinone was reduced to DSQ⁻ by a potassium mirror under vacuum. Parabenzosemiquinone was obtained from 1-4 benzoquinone by potassium mirror reduction in DME solvent. The spectrometer used for the investigations is described elsewhere^{2,4}.

RESULTS

DSQ⁻ K⁺ System : ESR spectral details of this system have been described in earlier papers^{2,4}. The present investigations were carried out with a view to predict the line shapes quantitatively using different models and to examine which of the models reproduces the experimental spectra in a faithful fashion. As described in our earlier papers^{2,4}, the spectrum at +60° consists of thirteen lines with binomial intensity distribution, coming from 12

1. E. A. C. Lucken, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 4234.
2. M. P. Khakhar, B. S. Prabhananda and M. R. Das, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1966, **45**, 2327.
3. E. E. Gough and M. C. R. Symons, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 269.
4. M. P. Khakhar, B. S. Prabhananda and M. R. Das, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 3100.
5. M. C. R. Symons, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1967, **71**, 172.
6. T. A. Claxton, J. Oakes and M. C. R. Symons, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, (In press).
7. D. H. Chen, E. Warhurst and A. M. Wilde, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, **63**, 2561.
8. B. S. Prabhananda, M. P. Khakhar and M. R. Das, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**.

methyl protons. At -60° the spectrum can be interpreted as coming from two different sets of six equivalent protons. At intermediate temperatures alternating line width effect varies with temperature. Maximum alternation is observed at $\approx -20^\circ$.

PBSQ⁻ K⁺ System : Although the room temperature values of the splitting constants obtained for this system by different investigators agree within experimental error, the values of the low temperature spectra show small differences. The low temperature spectrum of Warhurst *et al.*⁷ shows the presence of three overlapped spectra, one with a single splitting constant $a^H = 2.42$ G. The other two with splitting constants $a_1^H = 2.89$ G, $a_2^H = 1.95$ G and $a_1^H = 3.17$ G, $a_2^H = 1.69$ G. The low temperature spectrum obtained by the present authors⁸ has been interpreted as arising from two sets of two equivalent protons with splitting constants $a_1^H = 2.885$ G and $a_2^H = 1.935$ G superimposed on another spectrum, presumably from a free or solvated ion with a single splitting constant ≈ 2.41 G. Apart from these identified lines, there are also some spurious lines which cannot be easily interpreted. This situation suggests that the relative concentrations of the different types of the ion paired (PBSQ)⁻ depends on the purity of the sample and solvent and the care with which the sample is prepared. In fact, we have actually observed some differences among different sample preparations and the values reported have been obtained from a sample obtained by using freshly made quinone⁸.

*(PBSQ)⁻*K⁺* : PBSQ⁻ with ¹³C at the carbonyl carbon position has also been examined. The low temperature spectrum can be interpreted as coming from the overlap of two spectra one with $a^H = -2.41$ G and $a_1^C = a_4^C = -2.45$ G and the other with $a_1^H = -2.885$ G, $a_2^H = -1.935$ G, $a_1^C = -0.79$ G, $a_4^C = -3.50$ G. The room temperature spectrum can be interpreted in terms of one proton splitting ($a^H = -2.395$ G) and one carbon 13 splitting ($a^C = 2.04$ G). It has also been observed that the ¹³C satellites arising from the $M_H = 0$ lines are broader compared to the satellites from $M_H = \pm 1$ lines.

Line Width Studies : *(DSQ⁻) K⁺* : Earlier it was assumed that the alternating line width effects observed in this system arise from a temperature dependent equilibrium of the type

Calculations on line shapes⁴ show a reasonably good⁶ fit with experimentally observed spectrum with $k_1 = \frac{1}{\tau_1} = 3.00 \times 10^6$ Sec.⁻¹ and $k_2 = \frac{1}{\tau_2} = 2.00 \times 10^6$ Sec.⁻¹ for the -20° spectrum. However, the alternating line width behaviour of DSQ⁻Na⁺ system can not be explained by such a process. This has also been pointed out by Claxton *et al.*⁶.

Calculations were also done based on alkali metal migration model, where the same alkali metal is supposed to migrate between two equivalent sites within the radical

Extensive analysis of DSQ⁻K⁺ system has been carried out at different temperatures using alkali metal migration model. Rate constants at different temperatures are obtained by comparing the spectra at these temperatures with those calculated assuming different

values for the life time, τ , of a conformation. The first order rate constant k is $1/\tau$. With these values of k , a plot of $\log k$ vs. $1/T$ (Fig. 1) gives the first order rate constant $1/\tau$ to be $10^{11.14} \exp(-5267/RT)$ Sec.⁻¹. Similar calculations for DSQ-K⁺ in THF gives the rate constants to be $10^{11.63} \exp(-5964/RT)$ sec.⁻¹.

Fig 1 PLOT OF $\log k$ vs. $1/T$ FOR DSQ-K⁺ IN DMF

It should be pointed out that very good fits were obtained only after assuming a potassium splitting ~ 0.04 gauss. This is not unreasonable in view of the observed sodium splittings in DSQ-Na⁺ system.

(PBSQ-K⁺) system: No attempts were made to quantitatively compute the line shapes. This was because we have overlapped spectra from different species and estimation of line widths of different lines is impossible. However, the trends are similar to that predicted by the alkali metal migration model.

(PBSQ-*K⁺): In principle similar calculations can be done for the ¹³C lines. However, the conclusion based on comparisons of the widths of ¹³C lines is expected to be less accurate because of the approximations that have to be made. It is well known that the ¹³C satellites show pronounced changes in the line widths depending on the spin density on carbonyl carbon positions; and the sign of splittings. It should be added that the observed ¹³C line width behaviour with temperature cannot come from the equilibrium between ion paired and solvated species⁸. It is possible to explain the ¹³C line width effects using an alkali metal migration model.

Spin density calculations: Using the procedure described by the present authors elsewhere⁸, the spin density at the different positions in the ion-paired species has been experimentally evaluated. Table I shows the results of MO calculations made to fit the experimental spin densities with calculated spin densities using both the Hückel and the McLachlan methods.

TABLE I

Experimental and Calculated Spin Densities, p-Benzosemiquinone Ion-K⁺ in DME

Type of spectrum	Position	Spin densities		
		Exptal.	Calc ^{a,b,c,d,8}	
			McLachlan	Hückel
A-type (25°)	1	0.1512	0.1523	0.1516
	2	0.0885	0.0883	0.0887
	7	0.1718	0.1709	0.1711
A-type (A species, -75°)	1	0.1435	0.1436	0.1439
	2	0.0893	0.0891	0.0899
	7	0.1779	0.1783	0.1762
B-type C (B species, -75°)	1	0.1631	0.1591	0.1614
			(0.1615)	(0.1625)
	2	0.0717	0.0734	0.0754
			(0.0720)	(0.0771)
	3	0.1068	0.1053	0.1032
			(0.1043)	(0.1008)
	4	0.1334	0.1375	0.1359
		(0.1401)	(0.1410)	
	7	0.1591	0.1526	0.1538
			(0.1570)	(0.1535)
	8	0.1858	0.1934	0.1919
			(0.1890)	(0.1872)

^{a)} For A type at 25°, Coulomb integral parameters $\delta(7,7) = \delta(8,8) = 1.50$ and Resonance integral parameters $\gamma(1,7) = \gamma(4,8) = 1.28$ for McLachlan calculation and $\delta(7,7) = \delta(8,8) = 1.40$, $\gamma(1,7) = \gamma(4,8) = 1.16$ for the Hückel calculation.

^{b)} For A type at -75°, $\delta(7,7) = \delta(8,8) = 1.45$, $\gamma(1,7) = \gamma(4,8) = 1.30$ for the McLachlan calculation and $\delta(7,7) = \delta(8,8) = 1.35$, $\gamma(1,7) = \gamma(4,8) = 1.20$ for the Hückel calculation.

^{c)} For B type, within parenthesis, $\delta(7,7) = 1.50$, $\delta(8,8) = 1.40$, $\gamma(1,7) = 1.23$, $\gamma(4,8) = 1.30$ for McLachlan calculation and $\delta(7,7) = 1.44$, $\delta(8,8) = 1.35$, $\gamma(1,7) = 1.10$, $\gamma(4,8) = 1.20$ for Hückel calculation.

^{d)} For B type, without parenthesis, $\delta(7,7) = 1.53$, $\delta(8,8) = 1.43$, $\gamma(1,7) = 1.27$, $\gamma(4,8) = 1.31$ for McLachlan calculation and $\delta(7,7) = 1.42$, $\delta(8,8) = 1.32$, $\gamma(1,7) = 1.10$, $\gamma(4,8) = 1.22$ for the Hückel calculation.

^{e)} For B type, numbers without parenthesis are obtained by varying all the parameters, numbers within parenthesis are obtained by varying $\delta(7,7)$ and $\gamma(1,7)$ alone.

^{f)} For range of the parameters see Ref. 8.